

Policy Brief

Saying NO to development-forced displacement and resettlement: myths and alternatives

For 50 years, mainstream development thinking has legitimised the displacement and resettlement of people for large-scale projects such as dams, infrastructure and wildlife conservation. But half a century of evidence shows, indisputably, that displacement causes social, economic and environmental harm, and that it cannot be mitigated by resettlement. Despite this evidence, estimates suggest that the number of people displaced for development has risen drastically in the last few decades, from 10 million a year in the 1990s to 20 million in the 2010s (Cernea and Maldonado, 2018). Resettlement continues to be the preferred solution to overlapping claims on land. The three authors of this brief have each been working in and researching development-forced displacement and resettlement (DFDR) for 15-20 years in different parts of the world. We come together to express our shared conclusion: displacement causes irreparable harm, and well-intended resettlement policies and practices perpetuate and justify further displacement. Decades of experience and research demonstrate that it is impossible to get large-scale resettlement right. New policies must prioritise human-scale development that does not require displacement.

Five decades of evidence from operational evaluations, independent research and NGO investigations shows that displacement harms people, particularly vulnerable groups such as women and Indigenous peoples. It widens existing inequalities and carries steep hidden social, economic and environmental costs (Chambers, 1969; Hansen and Oliver-Smith, 1982; Scudder, 1962; Terminski, 2013; Cernea and Maldonado, 2018).

National and international policies governing displacement and resettlement were modelled on early World Bank policies that became the global standard. Agencies that finance

Personal belongings ready to be transported to the village's new location outside of the Limpopo National Park, Mozambique

This house, still inhabited, has a sign taped to the front that says, 'Notice to the public. Administrative demolition (forced demolition)' and has been painted with an X. The Philippines.

displacement projects created 'safeguards' to address the dismal resettlement outcomes, such as: (a) avoid displacement, or at least minimise its occurrence; (b) increase financial outlays for resettlement; (c) provide more and better training for resettlement practitioners; (d) improve the transparency and accountability of procedures involved in displacement and resettlement; (e) share the benefits of the project with displaced people; and (f) better align resettlement with broader global commitments to human rights, especially for vulnerable groups. But these safeguards do not lead to improved outcomes. DFDR is legitimised by a handful of cases considered to be examples of 'success', and five common myths.

Policy Highlights

1. Stop funding projects that displace people.

Governments, international development finance agencies and private corporations should stop funding projects that cause large-scale displacement. Only when displacement is no longer an option will in-situ, context-specific alternatives emerge.

2. Raise awareness of the systemic failures of resettlement projects.

Amplify awareness-raising campaigns in donor countries, strengthen international networks, and provide legal and other resources to local resistance movements.

3. Re-orient policies and investment towards non-displacing alternatives.

There are many approaches to development that do not displace people and that are also socially and environmentally sustainable; they require support through policy, research and investment.

4. Practise in-situ, human-scale development.

Integrate development infrastructure into the social and environmental landscape drawing on local, Indigenous and women's knowledges and without imposing mainstream development goals.

Myth 1: Displacement is inevitable for development

Displacement is argued to be inevitable for development. It is, rather, a consequence of one particular model of development. The model of 'development' that underpins the kind of projects that incur large-scale displacement is one that values wage labour, commodity production for markets and profit-seeking capitalist enterprises, separation of humans from nature, extraction of natural resources and male-centred perspectives. This model discriminates against small-scale, land-based livelihoods as well as women, rural dwellers and Indigenous peoples. The neoliberal tenets perpetuating the prevailing development model have left little room for development pathways based on other values. Historical conditions of marginalisation, such as neglect and oppression, make people displaceable. Conservation projects are sometimes seen as more 'justifiable' than other types of development projects because they are considered necessary to protect global biodiversity, but they often follow the same patterns and prioritise a singular pathway to development that excludes rural dwellers and facilitates the dispossession of their land.

Displacement as slow violence

Displacement is slow violence resulting from historic neglect and long-term structural marginalisation. This is exemplified by the Bui dam in Ghana. First conceived in the 1920s, the dam was only completed in 2011, providing plenty of time to make the land 'grabbable' and for the residents of the area to be made displaceable. Over decades, their political position was slowly undermined by the muddying of their legal rights to customary land through a number of small land acquisitions (see Wilmsen, et al. 2018 for full discussion). Then, in 1971, large swathes of Bui land were enclosed for the Bui National Park for so-called conservation purposes; the very same land that was later used for the construction of the Bui dam.

Promises of incorporation into the formal economy via the enormous "Bui City" (that never eventuated) and fair compensation were appealing enough that the majority of villagers resettled without resistance. Agreeing to move, they found themselves in a small resettlement village with basic infrastructure and few livelihood options, and now face ongoing impoverishment. Despite court action, 85% of people were never compensated for the loss of their land.

Partially demolished housing before resettlement in the Three Gorges Dam region, China.

Myth 2: Resettlement can bring development to displaced people

Resettlement is portrayed in policy as an 'opportunity for development', but research shows this to be misleading (Wilmsen et al. 2011; Chatterjee 2020). Resettled people may be provided with houses, roads and other essential infrastructure, but they are rarely provided with adequate jobs, their social networks fall apart, livelihoods are not easy to reconstruct, and women disproportionately carry the burden, leading to multi-generational poverty and insecurity. The benefits of resettlement usually accrue to already powerful groups within displaced communities and to those who are not displaced by the project. Therefore, rather than leading to development, resettlement widens existing inequalities and creates new ones.

How resettlement widens inequality

From 1998–2001, Adivasi from Kuno National Park in India were displaced from their fertile farms and forests and resettled on the edge of the forest on poor quality land with no forest access. They now earn a precarious income from farm wage labour or construction work in distant regions, and their farmland is largely under exploitative lease arrangements with non-indigenous groups at the resettlement site. Today, seven of the twenty-four resettled villages are facing yet another displacement, this time for an irrigation dam that will submerge their land to bring water to the farms of a more influential farming community downstream (Kabra, 2018).

The labour opportunities generated during and after displacement for setting up an industrial park in India went to cheaper migrant labour, while the poorest farmers who gave up their land in the hope of secure industrial employment only found short-term, low-paying work opportunities (Chatterjee, 2020).

Myth 3: Resettlement can be voluntary and consensual

Resettlement is formally considered to be 'voluntary' if full disclosure of all resettlement-related information is provided, and free, prior, and informed consent (FPIC) is given by all those relocating. But true volition requires that each affected person is accurately informed, understands the choices and has the right to refuse resettlement without fear of adverse consequences – yet this is hardly ever the case.

There are enormous benefits to labelling a resettlement voluntary. It is more likely to attract backing from international aid organisations because they can justify their involvement as altruistic. However, the politically-charged nature of displacement and resettlement, the power imbalances inherent in the process and the severity of what displaced people have to lose make true volition problematic (Milgroom and Spierenburg, 2008; Wilmsen and Wang, 2015). Coercion, manipulation, threats and bribes are commonly used, even in resettlements that claim participation, volition and consent.

The myth of voluntary resettlement

Common strategies used to obtain written documents signalling 'consent' from people displaced from parks and sanctuaries in India include long-term denial of basic infrastructure, removal of police check posts in insecure regions and the use of rumours and misinformation (Kabra and Mahalwal, 2018).

Similarly, research in China found that despite villagers having some say in whether or not they would resettle, the attitude of local cadres to those who would not move was that they “would eventually resettle even if it is in a coffin” (Wilmsen and Wang, 2015). Here, the government practices ‘coercion by deprivation’, whereby basic services are withdrawn and infrastructure is no longer maintained to deprive those who stay of their basic needs and eventually force them out. In Mozambique, World Bank officials threatened to release lions in the backyard of one of the villages living in the Limpopo National Park if they did not sign a document professing their volition to be resettled (Milgroom, forthcoming). What looks like volition and consent tends to be the result of deprivation, coercion, manipulation and violence.

Myth 4: People can meaningfully participate in resettlement and rehabilitation planning

Participation of people in the planning of their own resettlement has been incorporated into resettlement policies and guiding frameworks purportedly to improve outcomes and ease resistance to displacement. However, resettlement planning takes place in a context of power imbalances, fixed boundaries for what can and cannot be negotiated, tight timelines, opposing vested interests of multiple actors, micropolitics, and exclusionary practices, such as leaving women out of negotiations. These structural constraints thwart the best efforts of those committed to meaningful and genuine participation. Social development teams in funding agencies face strong resistance from colleagues whose careers depend on ‘moving the money’ via quick and resistance-free resettlements incompatible with participatory processes. An internal audit report of World Bank funded projects acknowledged that failure to implement proper resettlement is neither documented nor punished (Diagne, 2016).

Meaningful participation in resettlement planning is contradictory to state interests

In the resettlement of people from Mozambique’s Limpopo National Park, a ‘participatory’ planning process was imposed on an otherwise authoritarian government by European donors, in line with World Bank guidelines. Unaccustomed to citizen ‘participation’, issues that were fundamental for resettling people’s livelihoods, such as how much land they would receive or how they would provide for their cattle, were off limits. Instead, participation was focused on the details of the resettlement houses, such as the number of doors and windows, as a way to reduce their resistance to resettlement, and appease donors. Only male village leaders were allowed to participate in the negotiations about conditions for resettlement. When they expressed, for example, that they preferred to maintain traditional houses rather than brick houses, leave space between plots for future generations, to receive a manual water pump rather than an electric one, their preferences were overridden (Milgroom, forthcoming).

Myth 5: Resettlement can be successful if ‘best practices’ are followed

It is assumed that successful resettlement is a matter of adjusting controllable elements of the equation, that it is possible to ‘learn lessons’ from failed resettlement, and that ‘success stories’ can be replicated elsewhere. Rather than questioning the fundamental logic underlying resettlement, failure is blamed on a range of other causes: lack of

political will, funding and trained professionals; improper implementation of plans, etc. In practice, resettlement occurs in highly complex political, economic and social contexts in which many elements are neither measurable nor controllable. Uncritical belief in best practices normalises new rounds of harmful displacement.

Resettlement has been repackaged as a ‘science’ that is being taught through masters, diploma and certificate programmes in Resettlement Management in India, China, Europe and elsewhere. Academics, resettlement specialists and former development bank consultants train future resettlement practitioners from the Global South in the ‘best practices’ of resettlement. This perpetuates the myth that resettlement can be done well.

The Three Gorges Dam: best practice resettlement?

The Three Gorges Dam is generally considered an example of ‘successful’ resettlement. It is true that the reported social unrest was minor compared to the experience in other countries. The new cities, expressways, high-speed railway and special economic zones created seem remarkable, particularly to governments struggling with the intergenerational poverty caused by their own attempts at resettlement. However, the example of the Three Gorges is far more complicated. Around 30% of the population could not re-establish livelihoods due to the reduction in farmland and closure of industries in the region after resettlement (Wilmsen, 2016). Income growth was at least partially due to the rising tide effect of the overall growth of the Chinese economy during that period.

Cases like the Three Gorges are held up as an example of how resettlement should be done. For example, there is anecdotal evidence that officials from the Ghanaian government visited the Three Gorges, leading them to promote resettlement for the Chinese-funded Bui dam as a “development opportunity” for the displaced.

WHAT ARE THE ALTERNATIVES?

Displacement is not inevitable. It is a landscape management decision resulting from a particular vision of development. Development goals can be achieved without large-scale displacement by rethinking the type of development desired. Only when displacement is no longer an option will in-situ, context-specific alternatives emerge.

Instead of large-scale projects, water, energy, conservation and other needs can be met through locally appropriate, human-scale technological and governance interventions that are non-displacing and socially just (Mehta et al., 2019). Instead of enclosed solar parks, renewable energy can be generated in multi-use landscapes which assist local livelihood development (Nzila et al., 2021). Conservation of large species like tigers can occur successfully in landscapes inhabited by rural farming communities, instead of relying on creating inviolate parks through human displacement (Chanchani et al., 2016).

Non-displacing options include in-situ, human-scale approaches that prioritise local development and are co-produced with residents. Human-scale development is one that incorporates multi-use landscapes and local and indigenous knowledges, gives primacy to women’s perspectives and works with nature and existing adaptive practices as well as local cultures and identities.

WAY FORWARD

Widespread belief in these myths, and their reproduction through practice, policy and scholarship, is an obstacle to new ways of thinking about the relationship between development and displacement. We make four recommendations for a way forward:

1. CALL FOR A MORATORIUM ON FUNDING PROJECTS THAT DISPLACE PEOPLE:

International donors, development banks, private companies and governments must refuse to participate in initiatives that entail large-scale displacement.

- International networks of resettlement scholars and practitioners must pressure donors to stop funding displacement.
- Shame governments that agree to projects that cause large-scale displacement.
- Support communities identified for displacement to resist through campaigns, legal representation and resources.

2. RAISE AWARENESS OF THE SYSTEMIC FAILURE OF RESETTLEMENT

Media, civil society and community-based groups, transnational alliances, researchers and impact assessment professionals should unite to highlight the systemic failure of resettlement projects around the world.

- Organise global awareness-raising campaigns globally, nationally and locally.
- Require governments to disclose the numbers of people being displaced.
- Collate and circulate an open access repository of companies and organisations that displace people in the name of development and the effects of each case of displacement.

Stone wall erected to keep people out of the forest enclosed for the creation of a conservation area.

3. NORMALISE NON-DISPLACEMENT ALTERNATIVES IN POLICY

There are many development approaches that do not displace people and that are socially and environmentally sustainable. Policy attention is needed to mainstream them and scale them up. Development banks, international development agencies, private companies and philanthropists, the private sector and governments all have an important role to play:

- Shift policies towards prohibiting large-scale displacement and normalising non-displacement alternatives across the development sector.
- Make visible the hidden costs and intangible consequences of large-scale displacement and re-write financing rules to reflect the real costs.
- Train governments, development practitioners and consultants in non-displacing options.
- Invest in research and development of alternatives that prioritise existing human-scale approaches to make them viable and scalable.
- Develop public alternative in-situ technologies and approaches to assist planners.

4. PRACTISE IN-SITU, HUMAN-SCALE APPROACHES TO DEVELOPMENT

An in-situ, human-scale approach incorporates development infrastructure into multi-use landscapes using local, Indigenous and women's knowledges, and works with nature and existing adaptive practices. Plans must be co-produced and implemented with wide representation of local people to identify their preferred futures without imposing mainstream development goals that prioritise economic growth.

- Give primacy to local and Indigenous knowledges, worldviews, and cultures.
- Generate in-situ alternatives on a case-by-case basis.
- Identify and build on existing adaptive practices that strengthen the ecological, social and economic resilience of the project-affected people.
- Recognize peoples' rights to their land as an important step towards wellbeing.
- Work with the context of each location, including nature, geography and climate, and the concept of multi-use landscapes.
- Women's voices must be heard. Give priority to women's needs and perceptions.

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